

Synthesis and characterization of all inorganic Perovskites

$\text{CsPbX}_3, \text{RbPbX}_3$ ($X=\text{Cl}^-, \text{Br}^-, \text{I}^-$)

ABX_3

Thesis

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Abstract- Perovskites are ABX_3 structures, where A is larger cation, B is smaller cation, and X is anion. Recently, metal halide perovskites are studied widely because of outstanding optoelectronic applications. Rubidium halide perovskites are rarely reported perovskites. We report on the synthesis and characterization of colloidal rubidium lead iodide ($RbPbI_3$) nanowires (NWs). The length of NWs is found to be in micron. NWs absorb strongly below 445 nm. Based on morphological and optical properties, we predict the possible efficient use of NWs in photodetection devices rather than photovoltaic devices because of less absorption in larger portion of visible and infrared spectral range. Perovskites are used in photovoltaic application, as photo detector, optoelectronic application, color conversion LEDs. We synthesized Cesium lead bromide $CsPbBr_3$, cesium lead bromide beta cyclodextrin, Molybdenum perovskites and ternary perovskites. We measured their absorbance, photoluminescence, photoluminescence excitation and Time Correlated Single Photon counting, to measure life time or decay time of photoluminescence.

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Field of Study

Major Field: Physics

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Introduction- A perovskite is any material with the same type of crystal structure as calcium titanium oxide known as the perovskite structure. Perovskites take their name from the mineral, which was first discovered in the Ural Mountains of Russia by Gustav Rose in 1839 and is named after Russian mineralogist L. A. Perovski. General chemical formula for compound is ABX_3 . Where A atoms are larger than B atoms and X is anion. Different perovskite nanostructures find applications in various fields of science, specially in optoelectronics which includes solar cells, light emitting diodes, photodetectors, and lasers due to their superior bandgap tunability, high photoluminescence quantum yield, and charge transport properties over semiconductor quantum dots . This report presents synthesis and characterization of $RbPbI_3$ nanowires (NWs) and predicts possible applications based on obtained characterization results in photodetectors and study of nano-heterostructures which can further expand the possible use of these hybrid materials due to combined properties. Perovskite nanocrystals possess numerous unique attributes: defect tolerance, high quantum yield, fast rates of radiative decay and narrow emission line width in weak confinement, which make them ideal candidates for a variety of optoelectronic applications. Physical properties of interest to materials science among perovskites include superconductivity, magnetoresistance, ionic conductivity, and a multitude of dielectric properties, which are of great importance in microelectronics and telecommunication. They are also some interests for scintillator as they have large light yield for radiation conversion. Because of the flexibility of bond angles inherent in the perovskite structure there are many different types of distortions which can occur from the ideal structure. These include tilting of the octahedra, displacements of the cations out of the centers of their coordination polyhedra, and distortions of the octahedra driven by electronic factors (Jahn-Teller distortions). Perovskites are ABX_3 structures, where A is larger cation, B is smaller cation, and X is anion. Recently, metal halide perovskites are studied widely because of outstanding optoelectronic applications. Rubidium halide perovskites are rarely reported perovskites. We report on the synthesis and characterization of colloidal rubidium lead iodide ($RbPbI_3$) nanowires (NWs). The length of NWs is found to be in micron. NWs absorb strongly below 445 nm. Based on morphological and optical properties, we predict the possible efficient use of NWs in photodetection devices rather than photovoltaic devices because of less absorption in larger portion of visible and infrared spectral range. Perovskites are used in photovoltaic application, as photo detector, optoelectronic application, color conversion LEDs. We synthesized Cesium lead bromide $CsPbBr_3$, cesium lead bromide beta cyclodextrin, Molybdenum perovskites and ternary perovskites. We measured their absorbance, photoluminescence, photoluminescence excitation and Time Correlated Single Photon counting, to measure life time or decay time of photoluminescence.

Image Reference- Research gate

Instrument and Methods

Absorbance measurement Ultraviolet–visible spectroscopy or ultraviolet–visible spectrophotometry (UV–Vis or UV/Vis) refers to absorption spectroscopy or reflectance spectroscopy in part of the ultraviolet and the full, adjacent visible spectral regions. This means it uses light in the visible and adjacent ranges. The absorption or reflectance in the visible range directly affects the perceived color of the chemicals involved. In this region of the electromagnetic spectrum, atoms and molecules undergo electronic transitions. Absorption spectroscopy is complementary to fluorescence spectroscopy, in that fluorescence deals with transitions from the excited state to the ground state, while absorption measures transitions from the ground state to the excited state. In our lab we have instrument UV 2700 UV-VIS SPECTROPHOTOMETER SHIMADZU

Photoluminescence Measurement

Photoluminescence (abbreviated as PL) is light emission from any form of matter after the absorption of photons (electromagnetic radiation). It is one of many forms of luminescence (light emission) and is initiated by photoexcitation (i.e. photons that excite electrons to a higher energy level in an atom), hence the prefix photo-. [1] Following excitation various relaxation processes typically occur in which other photons are re-radiated. Time periods between absorption and emission may vary: ranging from short femtosecond-regime for emission involving free-carrier plasma in inorganic semiconductors [2] up to milliseconds for Phosphorescence processes in molecular systems; and under special circumstances delay of

emission may even span to minutes or hours. In our lab we have instrument of Agilent Technologies, Cary Eclipse Fluorescence spectrophotometer.

Photoluminescence Excitation measurement

Photoluminescence excitation (abbreviated PLE) is a specific type of photoluminescence and concerns the interaction between electromagnetic radiation and matter. It is used in spectroscopic measurements where the frequency of the excitation light is varied, and the luminescence is monitored at the typical emission frequency of the material being studied. Peaks in the PLE spectra often represent absorption lines of the material. PLE spectroscopy is a useful method to investigate the electronic level structure of materials with low absorption [3] due to the superior signal-to-noise ratio of the method compared to absorption measurements. In our lab we have instrument of Agilent Technologies, Cary Eclipse Fluorescence spectrophotometer.

Time Correlated Single Photon Counting

Time-correlated single-photon counting (TCSPC) is a well-established and common technique for fluorescence lifetime measurements, it is also becoming increasingly important for photon migration measurements, optical time domain reflectometry measurements and time of flight measurements.

The principle of TCSPC is the detection of single photons and the measurement of their arrival times in respect to a reference signal, usually the light source. TCSPC is a statistical method requiring a high repetitive light source to accumulate a sufficient number of photon events for a required statistical data precision. In our lab we have HORIBA SCIENTIFIC TCSPC

Transmission electron microscopy (TEM)

It is a microscopy technique in which a beam of electrons is transmitted through a specimen to form an image. The specimen is most often an ultrathin section less than 100 nm thick or a suspension on a grid. An image is formed from the interaction of the electrons with the sample as the beam is transmitted through the specimen. The image is then magnified and focused onto an imaging device, such as a fluorescent screen, a layer of photographic film, or a sensor such as a scintillator attached to a charge-coupled device. In our lab we have Tecnai F20 TEM.

Synthesis

Synthesis of RbPbI₃ in the lab:

Chemicals used

Rubidium carbonate (Rb_2CO_3), lead iodide (PbI_2), 1-octadecene (ODE), oleic acid (OA), and oleylamine (OAm), all are purchased from Sigma Aldrich. chloroform, toluene, and ethanol.

Preparation of Rb-oleate

Rb-oleate was prepared using typical metal-oleate method. 57.5 mg of rubidium carbonate Rb_2CO_3 , 5 ml of (ODE), and 0.315 ml of OA was heated in three-headed flask up to 120 °C under vacuum for 1 h. They formed clear solution. After stopping and cooling the reaction this solution makes white paste. This solution is injected in lead precursor solution, described in next lines, after heating little to make it clear solution again.

Preparation of Pb precursor solution

We again took a three headed flask and mix lead iodide (PbI_2) 43.35 mg (.094 mmol), 5 ml ODE, 0.25 ml of OAm, 0.5 ml of OA. When they are heated to 120 °C yellowish transparent solution is obtained.

Synthesis of RbPbI_3 NWs

1 ml rubidium oleate solution is added at 140 °C, yellowish solution of nanowires was obtained immediately after the addition. The reaction was quenched within 5 seconds in ice bath by putting the flask in ice. The solution was washed twice with methanol and toluene in equal ratio and centrifuged to get yellowish white paste. The nanowires in paste form can be dispersed in toluene or chloroform for further studies.

Microscope Images of RbPbI_3 NWs

The reported size of these NWs was several tens of micrometer [1]. Therefore, firstly, to get the idea of size of NWs, we performed simple optical microscope imaging. Sample was prepared by drop casting the diluted solution on cleaned silicone substrate and was dried under infrared light source. Since, the resolution of optical microscope is limited by the diffraction of light, we could not resolve the thickness of NWs which has been reported ~30 nm well below the diffraction limit of visible light. Photographs captured are shown below. The length of NWs ranges between 10 μm to 20 μm .

The scale in the images are 100 μm at 20X magnification, 20 μm at 50X resolution, and 10 μm at 100X resolution, respectively.

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Transmission electron microscope images

The Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) images provided the exact measurement of size and shape of the NWs.

Figure 4

Figure 4

The length on NWs found to be ranging between 2 μm to 20 μm which was not earlier completely resolved towards lower limit in optical microscope. The width of the NWs is between 10 nm-20 nm. The length and width of NWs is lesser than the reported value in reference [1]. The reason for that is immediate quenching of the reaction because of which there is no time for further growth of NWs. Also, the dimensions of NWs are large enough to be placed and manipulate with the help of simple optical microscope over 2-dimensional

(2D) layers of few micron size of different 2D materials like MoS₂, WS₂, graphene, GeTe, ReS₂, etc. to study charge transfer processes in hybrid 2D materials to further extend the possible applications which were not possible by single structure.

Synthesis of Cesium Lead Bromide

Synthesis of Cesium Lead Bromide in lab-

We used three headed flask for synthesis of CsPbBr₃. Firstly 69mg of lead bromide PbBr₂, 0.75 ml of oyl amine, 0.55 ml of oleic acid are heated at 120 °C, as Solution A and 0.4 ml of Cs oleate Solution B. Solution A and B are mixed and quenched after 5 second. Product is CsPbBr₃ greenish solution is formed with green luminescence. All solution is diluted with 2ml of acetone and 6 ml of toluene.

Transmission Electron Microscope Image of cesium lead bromide

Figure 5

Figure 6

Figure 7

Figure 5,6,7 represent TEM images of CsPbBr₃ nanocubes

Synthesis of Cesium Lead bromide beta cyclodextrin in lab

.2 mmol (22.4mg) CH₃NH₃BR,.2 mmol (73.4mg) of PbBr₂ , 30 μL hexamine . All are dissolved in 0.5 ml DMF under sonication at room temperature. Then 40 mg of β -cd was dissolved in 0.5 ml of precursor solution. Homogenous solution is formed. 0.3 ml of this

mixture was added to 5 ml of toluene, the color of resulting solution immediately changed to green.

Transmission Electron Microscope Images of Cesium lead bromide beta cyclodextrin

Figure 8

Figure 9

Figure 10

Figure 11

Figures 8, 9, 10, 11 represent TEM images of cesium lead bromide beta cyclodextrin

Synthesis of Molybdenum Perovskites in lab

20mg of MoCl_5 , 10ml ODE, .55 ml of oleic acid, 0.75 ml of oyl amine, .069 gm. of PbBr_2 . They form brownish orange transparent solution. 0.5 ml of Cs oleate in above quenched in ice after 5 second, orange color solution is formed.

Transmission Electron Microscope Image of Molebdenum perovskites

Figure 12

Figure 13

Figure 14

Figures 12, 13, 14 are TEM images of molybdenum perovskite

Synthesis of Ternary Perovskites in lab

Reaction A –

Cs_2CO_3 0.136gm, 7ml ODE, 0.4 ml of oleic acid, all are heated up to 120°C under vacuum

Reaction B

$\text{PbBr}_2 + \text{SnBr}_2 + \text{CuBr}_2$ (18.35+13.45+11.15) mg, 10ml ODE, 0.75 oyl amine, 0.55 ml oleic acid, are heated in three headed flask up to 140°C under vacuum

Then 0.4 ml Cs oleate are added in solution B. Quenched in ice after 5 second

Transmission Electron Microscope Image of Ternary perovskite

Figure 15

Figure 16

Figures 15 and 16 represent TEM images of Ternary perovskite

Results

Absorption spectroscopy of rubidium lead iodide perovskite

The absorption spectrum of NWs has maximum at 445 nm which gives an idea of band gap of around 2.8 eV. Since, the absorption is less in most of visible region towards red and if we extrapolate, in infrared spectrum due to which these NWs are less suitable for photovoltaic applications but can be used as photo detector.

CsPbBr₃ absorbance measurement

UV visible absorption for CsPbBr₃ nanotube of 9nm size. Absorption peak observed at 497 nm.

CsPbBr₃ small absorbance measurement

From graph we can see absorbance varies from wavelength 300nm to 525 nm. There is peak around 480 nm.

CsPbBr₃ cyclodextrin absorbance measurement

From graph we can see absorbance varies from wavelength 310nm to 510 nm. There is peak around 495 nm.

CsPbBr₃ cyclodextrin small absorbance measurement

From graph we can see absorbance varies from wavelength 320nm to 520 nm. There is peak around 490 nm.

Molybdenum Perovskite small absorbance measurement

From graph we can see absorbance varies from wavelength 310nm to 500 nm. There is peak around 445 nm.

Molybdenum Perovskite large absorbance measurement

From graph we can see absorbance varies from wavelength 310nm to 520 nm. There is peak around 470 nm.

Ternary perovskite small absorbance measurement

From graph we can see absorbance varies from wavelength 310nm to 510 nm. There is peak around 332 nm

Ternary perovskite large absorbance measurement

From graph we can see absorbance varies from wavelength 310nm to 520 nm. There is two peaks around 492 nm and 510 nm.

Cesium lead bromide CsPbBr₃ PL measurement excitation 325 nm

Photoluminescence of cesium lead bromide excited by 325 nm. Gaussian curve forms from 480nm to 530nm. There is peak PL at 513 nm with intensity 792au.

Cesium lead bromide CsPbBr₃ small PL measurement

Above graph is the photoluminescence of cesium lead bromide small excited at 325 nm. Gaussian peak starts around 450nm and ends around 540nm. There is peak around 512nm with intensity 685 au.

Cesium lead bromide cyclodextrin PL measurement excitation 325

Above graph is the photoluminescence of cesium lead bromide cyclodextrin excited at 325 nm. Gaussian peak starts around 460nm and ends around 530nm. There is peak around 515nm with intensity 692 au.

Cesium lead bromide cyclodextrin small PL measurement excitation 325

Above graph is the photoluminescence of cesium lead bromide cyclodextrin small excited at 325 nm. Gaussian peak starts around 460nm and ends around 530nm. There is peak around 509nm with intensity 696 au.

Molybdenum cesium lead bromide small PL measurement excitation 325

Above graph is the photoluminescence of molybdenum cesium lead bromide small excited at 325 nm. Gaussian peak starts around 470nm and ends around 530nm. There is peak around 457nm with intensity 345a.u.

Molybdenum cesium lead bromide large PL measurement excitation 325

Above graph is the photoluminescence of molybdenum cesium lead bromide large excited at 325 nm. Gaussian peak starts around 460nm and ends around 500 nm. There is peak around 476 nm with intensity 413a.u.

Ternary perovskites small PL measurement excitation 325nm

Above graph is the photoluminescence of ternary perovskite small excited at 325 nm. Gaussian peak starts around 470nm and ends around 550nm. There is peak around 526nm with intensity 376a.u.

Ternary perovskites large PL measurement excitation 325nm

Above graph is the photoluminescence of ternary perovskite large excited at 325 nm. Gaussian peak starts around 480nm and ends around 550nm. There is peak around 520nm with intensity 345a.u.

Cesium lead bromide PLE measurement excitation at 507nm

Above graph is for PLE measurement of cesium lead bromide, excitation at 507nm. PLE spectrum varies between 200nm to 500nm. There is peak around 303nm with intensity 987a.u.

Cesium lead bromide small PLE measurement excitation at 507nm

Above graph is for PLE measurement of cesium lead bromide small, excitation at 507nm. PLE spectrum varies between 200nm to 500nm. There is peak around 303nm with intensity 823a.u

Cesium lead bromide cyclodextrin PLE measurement excitation at 506nm

Above graph is for PLE measurement of cesium lead bromide cyclodextrin, excitation at 506nm. PLE spectrum varies between 200nm to 495nm.

Cesium lead bromide cyclodextrin small PLE measurement excitation at 506nm

Above graph is for PLE measurement of cesium lead bromide cyclodextrin small, excitation at 506nm. PLE spectrum varies between 200nm to 500nm. There is peak around 307nm with intensity 836a.u

Molybdenum cesium lead bromide large PLE measurement excitation at 417nm

Above graph is for PLE measurement of molybdenum cesium lead bromide large, excitation at 417 nm. PLE spectrum varies between 200nm to 405 nm.

Ternary perovskite small PLE measurement excitation at 512 nm

Above graph is for PLE measurement of ternary perovskite small, excitation at 512nm. PLE spectrum varies between 200nm to 500nm. There is peak around 305nm with intensity 465 au.

Ternary perovskite large PLE measurement excitation at 512 nm

Above graph is for PLE measurement of ternary perovskite large, excitation at 512nm. PLE spectrum varies between 200nm to 500nm. There is peak around 308nm with intensity 445 a.u.

Ternary perovskite small PLE measurement excitation at 519 nm

Above graph is for PLE measurement of ternary perovskite small, excitation at 519nm. PLE spectrum varies between 200nm to 535nm. There is peak around 303nm with intensity 38 a.u. There are various peak at this excitation.

TCSPC measurement of CsPbBr₃

Above graph is TCSPC measurement of CsPbBr3 excitation 390nm and prob 507nm, CsPbBr3 cyclodextrin excitation 390nm and prob 507nm. Lifetime graph extends from 20ns to 220 ns overall in all samples. This indicates lifetime of PL is around 200 ns in samples.

TCSPC measurement of molybdenum CsPbBr3 small and large.

Above graph is TCSPC measurement of molybdenum CsPbBr₃ large excitation 390nm ,molybdenum CsPbBr₃ small excitation 390nm .Lifetime graph extends from 25ns to 220 ns overall in all samples. This indicates lifetime of PL is around 200 ns in samples.

TCSPC measurement of Ternary perovskite small and large

Above graph is TCSPC measurement of ternary perovskite large, excitation 390nm and prob 510nm,ternary perovskite small excitation 390nm and prob510nm .Lifetime graph extends from 20ns to 220 ns overall in all samples. This indicates lifetime of PL is around 200 ns in samples.

Conclusion

We have successfully synthesized Rubidium lead iodide, Cesium lead bromide, Cesium lead bromide cyclodextrin .Molybdenum Cesium lead bromide and ternary perovskite in the lab. We have characterize all sample by measuring absorption, photoluminescence, photoluminescence excitation , transmission electron microscope images and time correlated single photon counting for measuring life time. We also find nanowires of rubidium lead iodide can be played over 2d material and from absorbance measurement we come to know it can be used as photo detector. Perovskite perovskites are studied widely because of outstanding optoelectronic applications. Physical properties of interest to materials science among perovskites include superconductivity, magnetoresistance, ionic conductivity, and a multitude of dielectric properties, which are of great importance in microelectronics and telecommunication. They are also some interests for scintillator as they have large light yield

for radiation conversion. Because of the flexibility of bond angles inherent in the perovskite structure there are many different types of distortions which can occur from the ideal structure. These include tilting of the octahedra, displacements of the cations out of the centers of their coordination polyhedra, and distortions of the octahedra driven by electronic factors (Jahn-Teller distortions) Due to their high photoluminescence quantum efficiencies, perovskites may be good candidates for use in light-emitting diodes (LEDs). However, the propensity for radiative recombination has mostly been observed at liquid nitrogen temperatures. In September 2014, researchers at EPFL in Lausanne, Switzerland, reported achieving water electrolysis at 12.3% efficiency in a highly efficient and low-cost water-splitting cell using perovskite photovoltaics . In 2008, researchers demonstrated that perovskite can generate laser light. LaAlO₃ doped with neodymium gave laser emission at 1080 nm. In 2014 it was shown that mixed methylammonium lead halide (CH₃NH₃PbI_{3-x}Cl_x) cells fashioned into optically pumped vertical-cavity surface-emitting lasers (VCSELs) convert visible pump light to near-IR laser light with a 70% efficiency. Perovskite are excellent in photovoltaic use. In our lab we synthesized 5 samples and characterize their optical properties.

Reference

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[https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Perovskite_\(structure\)#Applications](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Perovskite_(structure)#Applications)

